

JORDAN'S PATH TO PEACE: THE LEADERSHIP OF KING ABDULLAH II AND JORDAN'S MILITARY ROLE IN CONFLICT RESOLUTION

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Abstract

This study highlights Jordan's political and military strategies, taking into account Jordan's multifaceted approach to conflict resolution, with a particular focus on the significant role performed by His Majesty King Abdullah II. The study keeps a qualitative research approach while examining Jordan's capacity to use internal order, alliances, and diplomacy to settle regional disputes. Along with a well-trained military that portrays the country as transformative, the nation's efforts, directed by King Abdullah II's aspirational and visionary leadership on peace issues, also have a realistic political component. The study's findings include that Jordan has been able to use the politics of Middle Eastern conflict resolution to position itself as the peace broker. This study illustrates how Jordan's role and significance for enduring peace and stability in the area are enhanced by leadership, politics, and in this case, the military.

Keywords: Conflict Resolution, Regional Stability, Diplomacy, Mediation, Leadership.

INTRODUCTION

Jordan can arbitrate and settle long-standing disputes by striking a balance between international diplomacy and internal stability. In this regard, the study of *Jordan's Path to Peace: The Leadership of King Abdullah II and Jordan's Military Role in Conflict Resolution* looks at the nation's ability to use its diplomatic, military, and political tools to bring stability to an unstable region. Jordan has successfully navigated difficult obstacles, such as a sizable Palestinian refugee population and economic pressures. With the prudent and shrewd leadership of His Majesty King Abdullah II, he has been able to preserve its reputation as an honest peace mediator. Anziutti (2004) points out that Jordan's history outlines its practical strategy for reaching a consensus on security cooperation while maintaining solid regional ties.

Jordan is renowned for its ability to mediate Middle Eastern disputes, both internally and outside. Jordan's involvement in regional affairs has been strengthened by its handling of economic challenges, refugee integration, and public support for peace initiatives (AlMamani, 2013). In the face of escalating tensions, such as the recent Israeli-Hamas conflict, Jordan has demonstrated that it is a nation that takes its commitment to peace seriously by calling for ceasefires and talks. This study demonstrates how Jordan has become a secure stronghold at the center of domestic unity and strategic diplomacy for ultimate peace in the region because of King Abdullah II's political shrewdness and leadership, as well as a disciplined military.

Research Question

To what extent do the political and military policies of King Abdullah II and Jordan contribute to the settlement of Middle Eastern conflicts?

Research Objective

To look into how King Abdullah II's leadership has affected Jordan's conflict-resolution tactics, particularly how his diplomatic approach combined with the appropriate political and military structures has made Jordan the most vital mediator of Middle Eastern conflicts.

Study Problem

Given how problematic the Middle Eastern region might be, Jordan's role as a mediator in the Middle East has not been emphasized enough. Jordan's capacity to mediate conflicts has been refined in the political, military, and diplomatic spheres of power under His Majesty King Abdullah II. Although Jordan has achieved political success in the majority of the region's war zones, there is a knowledge gap on the successful interaction between Jordanian leadership, military strategy, and the domestic climate and how it affects the likelihood of lasting peace. King Abdullah II wants to see a respectful peace for all sides. Unfortunately, the internal factors contributing to stability in Jordan—such as the government's efforts to manage refugee settlements, address economic challenges, and garner public support for peace initiatives both domestically and internationally—are often underemphasized and overlooked by the international community. This occurs in the context of Jordan's significant role in conflict resolution within the Middle East and other conflict zones. For this reason, this study examines how Jordan's internal harmony under King Abdullah II strengthens the nation's mediation position concerning regional problems. This study looks at how, in addition to assisting the region in achieving peace, Jordan's leadership, military, and political policies maintain peace inside its boundaries so that domestic issues do not limit its capacity to mediate. This study demonstrates how Jordan's strategic leadership, military, and management combine to provide the tools required for the nation to mediate Middle Eastern conflicts effectively and, ultimately, help bring about peace and stability in the region.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Jordan has long been a pivotal Middle Eastern nation, and some scholars have examined its peace, security, and evolving sense of national identity. This Literature review discusses the various scholarly methods used to analyze Jordan's politics, military operations, regional policy, and strategic importance.

National Identity and Political System

In *Colonial Effects: The Making of National Identity in Jordan*, L. C. Brown & Massad (2002) examine and emphasize how the Jordanian military plays a crucial role in the performance and consolidation of nationalism, particularly in the postcolonial context, which by definition necessitates a unified institutional framework that upholds the

Hashemite regime in Jordan's various ethnic communities. According to L. C. Brown & Massad (2002), the Hashemite regime positioned the military institution at the center of Jordanian nationalism, which not only produced a sense of loyalty that encompasses different elements such as Islam, Arabism, and native Transjordan but also fostered a cohesive atmosphere under the vertical Hashemite order, which includes all social classes.

L. C. Brown & Massad (2002) discuss the need for the Jordanian military as a resource in the face of a swift and upsetting demographic shift, especially because of the 1948 and 1967 Palestinian inflows. These inflows are highlighted as previous issues, whereas Jordan has suffered from other upsetting demographic changes due to the inflows of refugees from Syria, Iraq, and other countries that experienced revolutions and setbacks. According to L. C. Brown & Massad (2002), by urging East Bank Jordanians and Palestinians to embrace a single national umbrella while maintaining East Bank leadership, the military was able to promote social unity rather than widen social divides. Loyalty to the king serves as a unifying factor among the populace as a result of this strategy, making the military's function in maintaining order and handling Jordanian divisions crucial.

The Military's Role in Stability

In his article *The Role of the Jordanian Army in Regional Stability: Its Role in the Arab Spring as a Case Study (2011–2016)*, Abudalbouh (2019) examines the issues of regional stability in light of the Arab World's changes, paying particular attention to the involvement of the Jordanian military. In this sense, Jordan, like the majority of its neighbors, maintained a rather stable domestic equilibrium; yet, the army as an institution had little influence over internal dynamics. Instead, it shifted its focus outside of itself and helped nations experiencing internal unrest. A thorough analysis of the issue showed that the army's history and professionalism qualified it as a regional force. For instance, Jordan trained forces from Libya to restore the security apparatus following Gaddafi and provided Bahrain with logistical and security support to enable them to maintain stability. Beyond its ability to fight, the army also provided logistical, educational, and humanitarian services. Accordingly, Abudalbouh (2019) points out that the stability of the area and Jordan's position as a nation that values peace throughout the challenging times were greatly aided by the Jordanian army's cooperation with international partners.

Regional Security and Diplomacy and Jordan's Diplomatic Leverage

Al-Dwairi (2001) explores the shifts in Middle Eastern relations that have occurred since the end of the 20th century when there was a noticeable shift in the region's structural dynamics from confrontation to cooperative peace initiatives. Al-Dwairi (2001) highlights how the Arab-Israeli conflict was strategically resolved by pursuing peace, cohabitation, and the common good rather than using force. Al-Dwairi (2001) asserts that security is crucial to this transformation because it has been, will continue to be, and has been a source of conflict in regional political relations and social processes. Al-Dwairi (2001) underlines those various factors of psychological and physical elements that are essential to the region's stability and contribute to its security. The history of the Arab-Israeli wars,

which continues to influence the attitudes of nations in this region, particularly concerning the danger to the security of the state of Israel, exacerbates this difficulty. Furthermore, the literature on cross-cultural integration implies that such peace can only be achieved in an area where countries may engage in constructive contact with one another, where this cooperation and engagement includes security measures that create the foundation for long-term stability (Al-Dwairi, 2001).

Al-Dwairi (2001) argues that regional security systems can be centered on non-military aspects like socioeconomic conditions, energy resources, water, ecology, population, and human rights, in addition to military ones, by looking to international models like the Organization for Security and Cooperation in Europe (OSCE). According to Al-Dwairi, a modified version of this model may be used in the Middle East to address the region's recurring issues while keeping its varied actors. According to Al-Dwairi (2001), the Middle East peace process and, more specifically, the execution of UN Security Council Resolutions 242 and 338 depend on the international order. Although European nations and the UN frequently support peace initiatives, the United States has been the most significant peace broker in the region's history. To succeed, the peace process must align with every Middle Eastern nation's national interest. However, due to the tremendous proliferation of weapons across countries and the pervasive political mistrust, these relevant regional security issues are unabated and pose a threat to peace and security (Al-Dwairi, 2001).

According to Al-Dwairi (2001), a long-lasting regional security regime will address the underlying causes of issues by implementing all-encompassing development initiatives that eradicate disparities and promote intergroup harmony. Al-Dwairi argues that Jordan's proposed security framework seeks to address a range of challenges by emphasizing three critical aspects: hard security to counter military threats, soft security that focuses on social and economic dimensions, and weapons control mechanisms. Due to its strategic geographic and political position, Jordan is a key player in the regional security landscape, facilitating political transitions and reinforcing stability in the area.

According to Sharp and Congressional Research Service (2024) in *Jordan: Background and U.S. Relations*, Jordan continues to be a vital U.S. ally in the Middle East, helping to maintain regional stability, combat terrorism, and advance the peace process in the Israeli-Palestinian conflict. Jordan and the United States have always had military, economic, and diplomatic cooperation, but during the year of tension, military aid and assistance—of which 75 percent is made up of military and economic assistance—significantly increased, helping Jordan reach the levels by fiscal year 2025. Jordan's peace treaty with Israel, its relationship with the Palestinians, and the present geopolitical events—particularly the wars in Gaza, Lebanon, Syria, and Iraq—all contribute to its geostrategic significance (Sharp & Congressional Research Service, 2024).

Sharp & Congressional Research Service (2024) also highlight Jordan's humanitarian activities in Gaza, where Jordan provides medical assistance and facilitates the delivery of relief supplies as a means of demonstrating the kingdom's commitment to lessening the suffering of the Palestinian people while preserving its diplomatic ties. Sharp &

Congressional Research Service (2024) also examine the expansion of Iran and its proxy forces in the region and how they threaten regional security, particularly that of Jordan, given their attacks on US troops inside Jordan's borders. This makes Jordan's regional security interests even more problematic.

According to Anziutti's (2024) article *The Role of Jordan in the Resolution of the Israel-Hamas Conflict*, Jordan has emerged as a key mediator in the Israeli-Palestinian conflict. It has been a stabilizing force due to its geographic placement in the middle of the crisis as well as the historical background of the nation's engagement with the Palestinian refugee problem. Jordan has managed the external pressure that led to the enormous number of Palestine refugees while maintaining the normalization of relations with Israel and being a major U.S. partner. Furthermore, the article emphasizes that King Abdullah II's policy is based on using diplomacy to try to break the impasse, which is required to prevent additional turmoil, particularly within Jordan. Anziutti (2024) also describes the attempts of the Jordanian government to bring the U.S. and other major powers together in an attempt to have Israel and Hamas bury the hatchet and Israel terminate its indiscriminate brutal murders and genocides in Gaza, even though these attempts have failed, as evidenced by the Gaza hospital incident that ruined the talks (Anziutti, 2024).

Anziutti (2024) argues that Jordan's diplomatic approach has evolved over time, as evidenced by the country's participation in global initiatives. Jordan possesses ample resources to promote peace and security in the region, thanks to its advantageous geographic location, the historical context of the area, and the various political events that have occurred there. The nation's commitment to maintaining regional stability is reflected in its consistent efforts in mediation, particularly in condemning wars. Additionally, Jordan demonstrates its ability to balance political influences and invests in diplomacy, especially within the context of the Middle East. Considering the internal political dynamics, military prowess, and even diplomatic initiatives in the region, this collection of literature demonstrates Jordan's vital role in the Middle East. In contrast, the kingdom's genuine desire for peace—mostly through regional focus and mediation—is deeply embedded in its cultural values and influences the key facets of its foreign policy in the face of the region's volatile politics.

DISCUSSION

Challenges and Opportunities: His Majesty's Vision for Jordan's Future Role in Conflict Resolution

Because of its position, diplomatic connections, and longstanding peacekeeping efforts, Jordan has been crucial in resolving regional disputes over the years, particularly under the reign of His Majesty King Abdullah II. In theory, Dajah (2024) in *Jordan's Role in Regional Conflict Resolution: Challenges and Opportunities under His Majesty's Vision* argues that international meddling is guaranteed by the King's vision for Jordan's future as a peacemaker since regional pacts and domestic consolidation will be promoted. Diplomacy and domestically focused political solutions with a healthy economy are

essential, despite the region's ongoing problems, including economic difficulties, security threats, and the ensuing instability.

Royal visions help Jordanians solidify their honor in their identity, like the 2002 *The Jordan First* campaign, which demonstrates how Jordan's national identity has always been sensitive to outside influences. In light of Jordan's position and difficulties within the Arab world, as well as its eastern border with Iraq and western border with Palestine, the Royal Vision of Jordan First aimed to advance an ideology of Jordanian nationalism (Köprülü, 2007). In *Consolidation of Jordanian National Identity: Rethinking Internal Unrest and External Challenges in Shaping Jordanian Identity and Foreign Policy*, Köprülü (2021) argues that Jordan's defense profile has also grown throughout this time, as seen by its membership in the OSCE and WTO as well as its classification as a Major Non-NATO ally of the United States. These alignments have contributed to economic change and integration into the global economy, as well as modernization efforts, particularly in the case of the Jordanian army (Köprülü, 2007).

In my view, King Abdullah II's strategy for Jordan is notably forward-thinking, effectively merging international cooperation with domestic reconciliation. By emphasizing strong external partnerships, His Majesty also seeks to rejuvenate the Jordanian identity, enabling the nation to evolve internally despite the regional challenges it encounters. The objective is to establish a Jordan that not only addresses external threats but also stands as a beacon of stability, modernization, and constructive development within the region. This approach highlights the importance of both adaptability and unity. His Majesty's emphasis on cohesion and strategic transformation demonstrates a long-term commitment to enhancing national power and international influence.

In line with his majesty's approach, according to Al-Dwairi (2001), Jordan plays a unique role in Middle Eastern diplomacy despite its tiny size and scarce resources. Jordan has adopted a pragmatic, non-aligned, and moderate foreign policy, which essentially permits only dialogue and the mutually agreeable resolution of conflicts, both of which are promoted and upheld. The Jordanian leadership's view of the region's changing security environment suggests a defense system built on non-strategic arms limitation, political agreements, and confidence-building. Al-Dwairi (2001), who focuses on those key areas, highlights Jordan's role as a peace broker and calls attention to the country's expenditures on UN security operations. Al-Dwairi (2001) posits that, beyond military considerations, a comprehensive approach to regional security and collaboration should encompass social, economic, and environmental factors, as well as address softer issues. Jordan's ultimate goal is to manage the competing interests in the Middle East and encourage interaction with outside parties to achieve regional peace and stability. I support Al-Dwairi's discussion and believe that Jordan's commitment to fostering regional collaboration, communication, and diplomacy across all boundaries has positioned it as a key stabilizing force in the Middle East. This demonstrates how small nations can promote security and peace effectively.

Building on Al-Dwairi's (2001) evaluation of regional security in the Middle East, I strongly believe that while Jordan's initiative to establish a regional security order is commendable,

there are significant practical and structural obstacles that must be addressed for it to be successfully implemented. A delicate balance between regional cooperation and the authority of individual states needs to be struck for the framework to function effectively. The geopolitical realities of the Middle East, characterized by long-standing animosities and hostilities, impede rapid progress and require a methodical approach that begins with establishing confidence before pursuing broader goals.

In my opinion, Jordan carries a dual responsibility: while it has the opportunity to lead, it also bears the weight of responsibility. Jordan's historical role in stabilizing the region and its strategic location in the Middle East have enabled it to minimize conflict in most regional crises. The country possesses the authority to intervene and support any security measures. However, due to its geographic position, Jordan is surrounded by conflicting regional and international interests, which necessitates the use of skilled diplomacy.

The security and reform situation in Jordan is precarious. Stability is understandable given the present events in the region, but real reform initiatives are hampered due to national security concerns. For progress to be sustainable, we need to know that stated security measures were imposed to effectively balance democratization and national security. Sharp and Congressional Research Service (2024) in *Jordan: Background and U.S. Relations* offers a crucial perspective on Jordan's precarious situation as it attempts to strike a balance between its relationships with other countries and its internal issues. Although Jordan's tight connections with the US and Israel are important for preserving the regional order, the country's predominantly Palestinian and Tribal descent population frequently expresses disdain for Israel's actions, especially in Gaza. Internal strife results from this, placing the indomitable supreme leader of the Jordanian Armed Forces King Abdullah II at a crossroads where he must choose between upsetting the populace or the kingdom's strategic intentions. In addition to these elements, the possibility of Iranian militias and dangers to Jordan's borders illustrates how unstable the situation is.

In addition to paying attention to the factors of conflict avoidance regarding cooperation with Iran and continuing to provide help to the people of Gaza, this effectively demonstrates Jordan's condition. As Sharp & Congressional Research Service (2024) tell us, maintaining Jordan's stability and cooperation with the United States in Middle Eastern foreign policy will depend critically on its ability to operate or endure such a dual and occasionally conflicting status.

According to Anziutti (2024), Jordan's role might be analyzed as that of a mediator and stabilizer during periods of heightened conflict. Egypt is in a similar situation, but Jordan has an extra ability in international politics because of its very close ties with the United States. In this regard, I would want to draw attention to Jordan's predicament: how to address the political and humanitarian crises within the nation without undermining the Palestinian people or offending its Western supporters. In addition to demonstrating the limitations of these objectives, the cancellation of the Amman summit also affirms Jordan's importance in terms of bridging the regions (Anziutti, 2024). The monarchy's demand for a ceasefire demonstrates a strong awareness of the boundaries at which regional or domestic order can be threatened (Anziutti, 2024).

Local and international authorities agree that Jordan is a key player in reducing tensions in the region during the ongoing conflict between Israel and Hamas. According to Kuttab (2023) in his article *Jordan Key to Resolving Current Conflict, Leading Officials Agree*, this is determined by the fact that Jordan has been able to successfully engage in mediation because of its positive relationship with the PA (Palestinian Authority), the existence of allies like Israel, and its longstanding ties with the US. Despite the exclusion of Hamas by forcing Hamas officials out of Jordan in 1998, Jordan's military and diplomatic prowess talks over the future of the Palestinian lands are incessant (Kuttab, 2023).

Jordan's close relationship with the United States and its historical ties to Israel and the Palestinian Authority make it a mediator in the long-running Palestinian-Israeli conflict. According to Kuttab (2023), Jordan's involvement in the conflict settlement process is also demonstrated by its role as a humanitarian player, which includes arranging aid drops in Gaza and supplying medical supplies and assistance, among other things, without having formal ties to Hamas. Instead of supporting temporary measures like who would rule over Gaza, Jordan can maintain both its respect and its stoic stance while acting as a reasonable party in the effort to find a just solution.

King Abdullah II, who participated in a combined operation to airdrop supplies into Gaza, stated that to prevent a worsening of what he described as a "catastrophic humanitarian situation," more aid must be provided to the war-torn region (Al-Khalidi, 2024). In a meeting with USAID chief Samantha Power, the monarch emphasized the pressing necessity for Israel to let the entry of food and other supplies into Gaza. To aid in the delivery of supplies to the northern region of Gaza, King Abdullah II also requested the establishment of more land entrance ports and the expansion of the current airdrop operations (Al-Khalidi, 2024). According to officials, Jordan is requesting that its Western partners support the provision of additional aid through the Kerem Shalom gate in addition to the Rafah crossing. Whereas Israel's officials claim that the flow of assistance supplies is unhindered, the amount of aid arriving from Egypt has drastically decreased recently; I deduce after having been watching the scenario of war perpetually and as it is known about the Israeli ideology of counterfeiting facts and adopting double standards, the Israeli propaganda has accused the UN and Palestinian officials of postponements. Subsequently, Al-Khalidi (2024) continues, King Abdullah took part in another, this time the largest-ever airdrop operation involving the air forces of Egypt, Qatar, France, and the UAE. Before the planes took off, King Abdullah II reportedly looked over the supplies of humanitarian aid. Airdrops have previously included materials for hospitals run by the Jordanian army in Gaza as well as medical supplies.

I believe that Jordan is a crucial party to the conflict in the Middle East because of its diverse and all-encompassing approach to conflict resolution. Although some restrictions on the operational involvement with Hamas may be seen as a hindrance, Jordan's longstanding relationships with Israel and the Palestinian Authority, along with the fact that it is an ally of the United States, provide it the capacity to support peace and dialogue efforts. Since the start of his reign, King Abdullah II has promoted a two-state solution, and all Jordanians' military and political views come with his majesty to a term and agree

with him that this stand-alone idea is the best and most sustainable way to resolve the Israel-Palestine problem.

Even after the peace treaty between Israel and Jordan was signed, tensions have persisted. According to Youvan (2024) in *Jordan's Evolving Role in Middle Eastern Conflicts: From Ancient Civilizations to Modern Diplomacy*, the internal situation in Jordan is still a mess, and because of the Israeli-Palestinian conflict's unresolved status, there is strong opposition to any kind of normalization with Jerusalem among the Palestinian community. As a result, any possible violation of Palestinian rights or change to the current situation in Jerusalem is certain to provoke popular outrage, which will have a detrimental effect on the two nations' bilateral relations. However, King Abdullah II has consistently maintained that the peace agreement is both required and advantageous for the Kingdom of Jordan's safety and well-being. His Majesty's advice continues to support communication, collaboration, and mutual respect as necessary conditions for preserving peace. Concomitantly, however, his Majesty King Abdullah II has been outspoken about his disgust with Israeli actions in the West Bank and Jerusalem, saying that they could stir the pot in the region and add to the level of violence (Youvan, 2024).

In his 2013 article *Evaluating Peace Agreements: The Jordanian-Israeli Peace Treaty of 1994, 16 Years Later: A Jordanian Perspective*, AlMomani (2013) examines the 1994 Jordanian-Israeli peace deal by evaluating the circumstances surrounding its signing and the subsequent relationship between the two nations. According to AlMomani (2013), many variables, including political survival, economic necessity, and security considerations—particularly given Jordan's proximity to Israel and its involvement in the Arab-Israeli conflict—led to the country's relationship with Israel in a peace-making discussion. Although both nations were fully committed to the peace pact, regional factors—primarily the Israeli-Palestinian conflict—have influenced the development and speed of their interactions.

According to AlMomani (2013), since the 1994 signing of the peace accord, relations between Israel and Jordan have remained largely cordial. However, because of the ongoing absence of peace between Israel and Palestine and the violent relationship between the two nations, the treaty has not been completely implemented, among other things affecting the economy of Israel and Jordan. AlMomani (2013) also examines the impact of both internal and external politics on Jordan-Israel relations, particularly during the tenure of Israeli Prime Minister Benjamin Netanyahu, who assumed office in 2009 (AlMomani, 2013). Nonetheless, the Israeli government's stance on the Palestinian cause is the main reason why the Jordanian populace still vehemently opposes normalization with Israel. AlMomani (2013) notes that while the peace treaty has certain positive aspects, such as security and even some degree of economic engagement, its full realization is thwarted by larger regional dynamics and conflicts, most notably the Israeli-Palestinian conflict.

Based on AlMomani's (2013) perspective, I construe that the 1994 Jordan-Israel peace pact shows a delicate and complex employing a strategic balance between the issues and interests in that area. Both states have upheld their end of the bargain thus far, but

the full potential of their engagements is constrained by the current absence of a more comprehensive resolution to the Israeli-Palestinian conflict. Bilateral ties have been strained and frustrated as a result of the region's instability and changing political landscape since the Oslo Accords were signed (AlMomani, 2013). However, I believe that a more comprehensive peace, particularly one that tackles the Palestinian question, will significantly accelerate and intensify Jordan-Israeli relations, resulting in greater collaboration on diplomatic, security, and economic matters. However, there are also political issues and public skeptics, like in Jordan, which demonstrate that establishing peace in the region is not an easy undertaking.

As a result, Jordan has also been assertive in advancing its reputation as His Majesty King Abdullah II honorably for us, Jordanians, is the custodian of holy sites in Jerusalem. Jordan engages in lobbying efforts to uphold the current structure and avoid any provocations. According to Youvan (2024), Jordan's diplomatic efforts include direct talks with Israel, France, the United Nations, the Palestinian Authority, and other Arab and Muslim nations. King Abdullah II has stated unequivocally that any action intended to undermine Jordan's custodianship or alter Jerusalem's status will have disastrous effects on regional peace and security. Jordan's approach to maintaining peace with Israel while supporting the Palestinian cause, in my opinion, demonstrates the significance of the nation in regional diplomacy. One of the key reasons Jordan is still viewed as a mediator in regional disputes is King Abdullah II's unwavering focus on upholding Jerusalem's order and advancing the Palestinian cause (Youvan, 2024). Jordan's approach to maintaining peace with Israel while supporting the Palestinian cause, in my opinion, demonstrates the significance of the nation in regional diplomacy. One of the key reasons Jordan is still viewed as a mediator in regional disputes is King Abdullah II's unwavering focus on upholding Jerusalem's order and advancing the Palestinian cause.

The key feature in the case's approach to the two-state solution in dispute—Palestine and Israel—is highlighted in Bdour's (2021) article, *Jordan's Mediation Leverage in the Israeli-Palestinian Conflict: Making Use of the Regional Momentum*. The nation's characteristics include its strategic location, which is similar to geography, its active participation, which is similar to participation, and its mediation. According to Bdour (2021), the king's political prowess and military professionalism helped in enhancing diplomatic ties with the international community. Bdour (2021) highlights the necessity of strengthening multilateral strategies, learning from previous mediation failures, and creating frameworks that would eventually support continued peace initiatives. According to Bdour (2021), the capacity to carry it out hinges on Jordanian diplomacy's ability to involve all relevant parties and conduct routine diplomacy for the most urgent issues of the day, such as settlements, Jerusalem, the establishment of a Palestinian state, and so forth. She made the demand that any future attempts at mediation must be made well in advance, entailing a great deal of traveling and the creation of new tools for future peace.

In his article published in *Jordan Times*, *Jordan and Promoting Regional Peace: Challenges, Prospects*, Dajah (2024) highlights Jordan's strategic location and significance in Middle Eastern regional politics, with an emphasis on fostering peace and preserving stability. Despite the numerous challenges it faces, Jordan has benefited from

a reputation as a neutral party capable of mediating disputes, which has enhanced its national stature. These include security risks posed by regionally powerful forces, such as the Syrian conflict, the Israeli-Palestinian conflict, and the Iraqi crisis, which has put a burden on the kingdom's infrastructure and economy. According to Dajah (2024), the country's economy has also been made more complex by its reliance on foreign aid and the ongoing refugee crisis. Jordan continues to support its regional peacebuilding efforts and aid those affected by intra-state conflicts in neighboring countries, even though there are obstacles to overcome, such as the current state of affairs in the region.

With the Israeli-Palestinian conflict at the forefront of its foreign policy, Dajah (2024) ascertains that Jordan's mediation has been especially successful. Jordan's moral stance of upholding the sanctity of Jerusalem and defending Palestinian rights is undeniable, although the Palestinian issue is still developing on more complicated and nuanced fronts in history. Dajah (2024) also highlights Jordan's capacity to strengthen regional cooperation in addressing common issues like economic downturns, climate change, and counterterrorism. Because of this Western Arabic mediation and its advantageous geographic location, the entire region may benefit from the growth of trade and collaboration. Furthermore, Dajah (2024) adds that Jordan may strengthen its power by implementing political and economic reforms within the country. This will help it better handle regional problems and serve as a major regional stabilizer.

I firmly believe that one of the most important factors for Middle Eastern peace and stability is Jordan's readiness to uphold peace. This makes sense given that Jordan is dealing with several issues, both overt and covert. However, Jordan has remained steadfast in its support of mediation nonviolent dispute settlement, and conflict resolution. To get the most out of its peacekeeping assistance. While regional security is important, the economy of Jordan is to be improved. Jordan's ability to handle regional conflicts will greatly increase with a stronger economy and a well-run government, which will then more effectively support regional peacebuilding initiatives.

The initiatives of peacebuilding have been global through the omniscience of His Majesty King Abdullah II with his great concern to have the Jordan Armed forces cooperate with international peacekeeping organizations. The participation of Jordan Armed Forces began back in the beginning of the '90s when King Hussein ordered to dispatch of peacekeeping operations to Croatia. Interestingly, many Jordanian officers sacrificed in favor of placing Jordan's imprints of peace everywhere in the areas of conflict. Jordan Armed Forces, in my opinion, has emerged as one of the most significant stabilizing elements in the region during its most tumultuous periods. If not to bolster Abudalbouh's (2019) long-held belief, I think Jordan's internal integrity was the reason the army looked to outsiders who were able to assist nations in the area without jeopardizing the Kingdom's internal security. Abudalbouh (2019) presents a compelling argument for how these outside interactions improved Jordan's political and economic standing. By taking part in international peace support operations, the Jordanian military has bolstered its claim and engagement as a major player in the security of both regional and global dimensions, ensuring the kingdom's survival in an otherwise unstable area. The table below shows the history of the Jordan Armed Forces' participation in international

peacekeeping operations. I extracted the following data from the (*The General Command of the Jordanian Armed Forces the Arab Army, 2024*).

Participation in Previous UN Tasks (Forces) until December 31, 2014

Unit/Mission	Start Date	End Date
Jordanian Protection Battalion/1 Croatia	1992/03/12	1995/07/03
Jordanian Protection Battalion/2 Croatia	1993/09/05	1995/09/25
Jordanian Protection Battalion/3 Croatia	1993/12/11	1995/09/19
Jordanian/Bosnia Possibility Company	1994/04/04	1996/06/18
Jordanian/Bosnia Special Duty Team	1996/02/14	1998/12/19
Housing Management Officers/Angola	1996/03/12	1997/11/24
Jordanian Protection Battalion/4 Croatia	1996/03/24	1997/07/30
Plisso Warehouse Guard Platoon	1996/08/22	1997/11/30
First Peacekeeping Force/Kosovo	1999/10/15	2001/09/22
Peacekeeping Force II/Kosovo	1999/10/31	2001/10/24
Peacekeeping Battalion/Timor	2000/01/17	2002/01/31
1st Peacekeeping Battalion/Sierra Leone	2000/04/08	2000/12/16
Freetown/Sierra Leone Cutter Command	2000/04/11	2000/12/24
2nd Peacekeeping Battalion/Sierra Leone	2000/05/22	2005/12/24
Medical Secrecy/Sierra Leone	2000/05/29	2001/01/27
Jordanian/Ethiopia and Eritrea Peacekeeping	2000/12/22	2008/03/23
Jordanian Medical Company/Eritrea	2000/12/19	2008/02/28
Third Line Hospital/Sierra Leone	2001/01/16	2005/10/21
Second Line Brundy Hospital	2004/10/01	2005/10/01
Jordan's 1st Peacekeeping Battalion/Haiti	2004/11/25	2006/06/24
Asmara Military Police Faction	2006/01/13	2007/01/13
Haiti Peacekeeping Group Command	2005/10/11	2004/03/03
Third Line Hospital/Liberia	2003/11/24	2014/07/11
Jordanian Peacekeeping Force/Ivory Coast	2005/08/27	2014/06/09
Second Line Hospital/Congo	2006/07/20	2014/09/15
Jordanian Peacekeeping Battalion/Ivory Coast	2006/08/22	2014/11/18
Abidjan/Ivory Coast Cutter Command	2011/03/25	2014/11/18

For further information, please see the link below:

https://www.jaf.mil.jo/ContentstemplateC/Other_Participations.aspx

Jordan is considered one of the leaders in the fight for peace and security, both locally and globally. As a nation dedicated to the maintenance of international order, Jordan is an active troop-contributing nation and also engages in dialogue and mediation. In addition to being one of the nations that contribute the most troops to UN peacekeeping operations, Jordan also deploys police forces, including female police officers from Jordan. As part of our ongoing commitment to enhancing women's participation in peacekeeping missions, more women will be involved in such missions (*Jordan Peacekeeping, 2017*).

In *The Role of the Military Institution as a Major Factor of the Political Stability in Jordan*, Abdullah (2022) attempts to investigate the significance of Jordan's military institutions concerning political stability. The analysis argues that in addition to defending national borders, the military may also be able to carry out developmental tasks including fostering

economic expansion and change. When regional or international politics meddle, Abdullah (2022) emphasizes that the military is also essential to preserving political stability and order in the nation. The claim that political stability can only be understood and attained by tools of coercion and control, particularly during turbulent times like the Arab Spring, is refuted in this study, which is typical of most investigations of the phenomenon.

Abdullah (2022) asserts that a more humanistic approach to providing stability typically yields better results, highlighting the necessity of striking a balance between security and other factors. According to Abdullah (2022), the military's role in Jordan has evolved from being solely protective to actively contributing to the country's development. Because of this dual duty, the army has been able to play a key role in reestablishing political and economic order as well as protecting the country's boundaries. Abdullah (2022) emphasizes how important it is to include the military in political endeavors, particularly in the fight against the emerging threats of terrorism and extremism. Abdullah (2022) also makes the case for the necessity of responding to internal issues, whether they result from humanitarian operations involving refugee floods into neighboring nations or from beyond them.

Abdullah (2022) further argues that the military's flexibility—the ability to carry out various tasks according to the geographical, social, and political context—is responsible for the ease with which it has been able to establish and uphold order. The military's success has been attributed to its institutional capability, comprehensive understanding of national security, and—most importantly—the ability to adapt its tactics in reaction to the political and social environment. Abdullah (2022) suggests enhancing the Ministry of Defense's oversight of military operations, reforming the security framework to counter both conventional and unconventional threats, and incorporating the skills of strategists, scientists, and retired soldiers into Jordan's development. Additionally, Abdullah (2022) promotes public focus on the military's roles, particularly among youth, and calls for ongoing national dialogue to implement social and political reforms that could prevent future unrest. Abdullah's (2022) study limitations unequivocally state that the military plays a vital role in maintaining Jordan's political system, both in its armed capacity and in other facets of society.

Based on the study of Abdullah (2022), I argue that the military institution in Jordan plays a crucial role in maintaining political order in the nation, not only by imposing military rules but also by supporting economic growth and the modernization of the security forces. The military will remain a component of stability as long as it can adjust to shifting regional and international circumstances and participate in domestic political processes. My study coalesces with Abdullah's (2022) study in challenging the notion that has been claimed by other researchers, who hold opposing views to Jordan, that overwhelming force is the only way to preserve low levels of order, particularly in chaotic periods like the Arab Spring, and promotes a more compassionate perspective. Additionally, changing ignorant beliefs that are only heard by those who call themselves political resisters is crucial for Jordan's stability and security in the future. Having illuminating political and military omniscience like the unique discretion and prudence of His Majesty King Abdullah II is

crucial since it calls for enhancing the Ministry of Defense's role, enhancing regional stability in the Middle East, modernizing security systems in Jordan, and utilizing the capacity of both civilian experts and former service members in the service of Jordan.

In her review of King Abdullah II's book *Our Last Best Chance: The Pursuit of Peace in a Time of Peril* (2011), Sütalan (2021) considers the book as both regionally political and autobiographical. The Israeli-Palestinian conflict is the primary topic of King Abdullah II's book, which covers his life from boyhood to the time he took the throne. King Abdullah II (2011) argues for the necessity to stop the war, which he feels is the primary source of all the issues in the territorial region, and rejects earlier attempts to broker peace, particularly the methodical approach of diplomacy. According to King Abdullah II (2011), the resolution of the Israeli-Palestinian problem is a worldwide issue that affects many Muslims deeply rather than just being a regional one. King Abdullah II (2011) emphasizes the necessity of US assistance in the peace process and chastises Israeli leaders, including Netanyahu, for breaking peace commitments. Furthermore, despite acknowledging that the Arab Peace Initiative faces numerous challenges, including regional instability and division among the Palestinian leadership, King Abdullah II (2011) supports the idea. All things considered, the book is still a pertinent work that urges an expedient resolution to the Israeli-Palestinian issue in light of its implications for the surrounding area and the wider world.

In addition to His Majesty's King Abdullah II compositions that have influenced intellectuals around the world, his Majesty's eloquence, and effectiveness in English have been praised internationally. In his article, *The Linguistic Functions in King Abdullah II of Jordan Speeches*, Mohammed (2019) examines how King Abdullah II of Jordan uses language in his press appearances, political speeches, and conference engagements to command and influence public opinion. Discourse analysis techniques were scrutinized in that study. Mohammed (2019) regards the works approach to analyzing the king's communication as focusing on the strategies of achieving coherence: the quality, quantity, relevance, and manner of the communication as proposed by "Grice's maxims; Van Dijk; Fairclough; and Johnson and Johnson's models to study both the persuasion styles and persuasion strategies he maintained in his speech." (Mohammed, 2019, p.1). Mohammed (2019) scrutinizes King Abdullah II's discourse tactics in his speeches, emphasizing how he uses language to establish a secure, welcoming environment and uphold Grice's principles of quality, quantity, relevance, and manner. The King clearly and optimistically communicates his thoughts through the use of persuasive strategies like reiteration, intertextuality, and modality. He used a "stick and carrot" strategy in his address, denouncing Islamists as "Khawarij" but also suggesting that they might modify their beliefs (Mohammed, 2019, p.7). Mohammed (2019) urges curriculum designers and political science students to scrutinize political speeches like King Abdullah II's to gain a deeper understanding of the persuasive techniques used by seasoned political figures. Mohammed (2019) suggests that political speeches like these should be carefully read to reveal hidden meanings. I agree and support Mohammed's (2019) analysis of King Abdullah II's speeches, and I ascertain that His Majesty's speeches are not only clear and hopeful in their meaning, but they also employ compelling linguistic techniques that

guarantee the speech's structure and coherence. Furthermore, these speeches have a lot more to offer language studies and political discourse research.

The political and democratic influence and indomitability of His Majesty King Abdullah II have been further discussed and supported by several academicians in the field of politics and democracy. In their article, *The Political Impact of King Abdullah II's Second Discussion Paper on the Development of Jordan's Democratic System: An Analytical Study of Political Parties (2013-2024)*, Hamdon et al. (2024) investigated the political effects of King Abdullah II's Second Discussion Paper on Jordan's democratic growth on political parties between 2013 and 2024. In democratic theory, a political analysis aims to quantify the impact of the Discussion Paper (an independent variable) on the growth and influence of political parties (a dependent variable). Crucially, the analysis found that the Second Discussion Paper had mediated national discourse, significantly increased political plurality, and ultimately led to legislative reforms that strengthened the role of political party activity in the democratic process. A precedent for better party representation and perhaps better parliamentary government formation will be established by the 2024 elections. This study shows that the Discussion Paper had a fundamentally important role in changing the political landscape of Jordan by encouraging group action, strategic planning, and improved citizen representation (Hamdon et al., 2024). The analysis of Hamdon et al. (2024) demonstrates how King Abdullah II's Second Discussion Paper acted as a catalyst for changes to Jordan's democratic system. In my opinion, strengthening pluralism and political parties not only strengthens a democratic system but also makes the state more resilient to local and international threats. Another step in the direction of a more inclusive and participatory democratic system is the apparent progress made in the 2024 elections. This illustrates how effective visionary leadership can be in enacting significant reforms.

The philosophy of leadership of His Majesty King Abdullah II is a school of thought to be didactic, moralizing, and educational in the field of politics and diplomacy. In *A March towards Reform: The Metaphorical Conceptualisation of 'Reform' in King Abdullah II's Language*, El-Sharif (2015) investigates how King Abdullah II of Jordan conceptualizes and expresses the concept of "reform" in his political speeches by using metaphor, specifically from the PATH and CONFLICT domains. It provides a metaphorical understanding of reform as a protracted and arduous process that calls for everyone to make a sacrifice and, occasionally, to endure. Therefore, it may be claimed that PATH metaphors offer reform as a collaborative effort in which Jordanians are "travelers" en route to a shared goal, but CONFLICT metaphors conjure images of sacrifice and strength, portraying reform as a military operation.

His Majesty King Abdullah II emphasizes that reforms are a necessary condition for stability and progress in his country; as such, he is seen as a leader who is actively involved in that process El-Sharif (2015). El-Sharif (2015) notes that although the King discusses comprehensive transformation, such as an elected government, he also acknowledges that these reforms are slow and continuous. While not completely discounting the reform's final manifestations, this wording aims to comfort the public and set reasonable expectations for the process (El-Sharif, 2015).

King Abdullah II has deliberately employed metaphorical language to characterize reform as a slow, group process, as El-Sharif's (2015) study shows. I see that the delayed pace of the changes is a reflection of the intricate dynamics Jordan faces on a regional level. Such prudence maintains political stability while striking a balance between the conditions needed to bring about change in a very unstable setting. During a period when the nation is forging its path toward reform amid intense regional and global pressure, the King's discourse goes further in controlling public expectations and fostering them toward resilience and unity.

METHODOLOGY

Using a qualitative research methodology, this study employs a case study design focusing on Jordan's military and political approaches to conflict resolution, highlighting the part played by His Majesty King Abdullah II. This investigation is especially well-suited for qualitative research since it enables a thorough examination of military dynamics, political decision-making, and leadership in a regional setting.

Key Focus Areas

National Identity and Political System

This theme looks at how Jordan's political structure and sense of national identity support its stability and conflict-resolution skills. The paper examines how Jordan's political environment has been shaped historically, by social cohesiveness, and by constitutional frameworks.

The Military's Role in Stability

The ability of the Jordanian Armed Forces (JAF) to serve as a stabilizing force is assessed in this focus area. In order to preserve internal order and portray Jordan as a transformational power, the analysis looks at military modernization and training.

Regional Security and Diplomacy

The study looks on Jordan's diplomatic clout and approach to regional security. Particular focus is placed on Jordan's efforts to mediate conflicts between Middle Eastern states, its position in regional forums, and its strategic partnerships.

Challenges and Opportunities: His Majesty's Vision

The study explores His Majesty King Abdullah II's visionary leadership and highlights his initiatives for Jordan's future role in conflict resolution. It analyzes chances to increase Jordan's diplomatic influence while pointing out obstacles such resource shortages and geopolitical instability.

Data Analysis

A thematic analysis is performed on the gathered qualitative data. Relevant ideas on conflict resolution and Middle Eastern geopolitics are used to identify and understand key themes, including leadership, military tactics, diplomacy, and regional alliances. The

study's ability to capture the complex ways in which Jordan uses its resources and peace-building tactics is guaranteed by the theme analysis:

- **National Identity and Politics:** Examining how stability, political structure, and national identity interact.
- **The role of the military:** Assessing the JAF's contributions to peacekeeping and stability.
Analyzing Jordan's partnerships and negotiating tactics in the context of diplomacy and regional security.
- **Opportunities and Challenges:** Evaluating King Abdullah's vision's real-world effects on Jordan's position as a regional leader.

Using a case study design, the research focuses on Jordan as a single case to comprehend its complex strategy for resolving regional disputes. This method makes it possible to examine in great depth how Jordan's role as a Middle East peace broker has been shaped by the interaction of political leadership, military prowess, and diplomatic involvement. Themes and narratives in speeches, official documents, and foreign diplomatic correspondence affecting Jordan are examined using content analysis. This approach draws attention to the military and political debate concerning Jordan's role in resolving disputes.

FINDINGS

The study shows how Jordan has successfully used military and political tactics to settle Middle Eastern disputes under His Majesty King Abdullah II. Jordan is therefore a key player in peace efforts because of its multifaceted approach to conflict resolution, which combines diplomacy, regional relationships, and internal stability. The study has shown that Jordan is poised to become a powerful force for stability in the future thanks to King Abdullah II's inspiring and visionary leadership and a well-trained and disciplined military.

The study shows that both internal management and external diplomacy are necessary for Jordan to be an effective mediator. Jordan's involvement in regional conflict resolution was enhanced by the country's structural internal order, refugee integration, poverty, and popular support for peace initiatives. Nonetheless, these results show that Jordan is a credible and successful peace broker in the Middle East due to the harmonious interaction of political savvy, military readiness, and visionary leadership of His Majesty King Abdullah II.

CONCLUSION

Under King Abdullah II's rule, Jordan's strong military and political policies were reinforced by its strategic leadership, making it a crucial player in Middle Eastern conflicts. The study concluded that Jordan's special position as a peace broker stems from striking a balance between maintaining domestic stability and using a practical approach to both military strategy and diplomacy. Jordan has demonstrated under King Abdullah II's rule that it is capable of supporting both regional peace initiatives and maintaining a stable internal

climate that strengthens its mediating powers. In the end, this study demonstrates that Jordan's ability to resolve disputes goes beyond conventional mediation. Jordan has become one of the pillars of peace and stability in the region by combining military change, visionary leadership, and domestic unification into a unified national agenda. Jordan will always be seen as a ray of hope for Middle East peace thanks to this combination of internal and external policy.

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